

Gridded mapping of unvaccinated children in conflict settings: a tailored approach

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Summary

This paper proposes a new method to map conflict-affected children which is tailored for vaccination research. The method accounts for geographic proximity and multiple conflict characteristics and produced a gridded dataset that allows for multi-scalar analysis. This method is an improvement upon previously used methods. It simultaneously summarises national and international trends while also preserving subnational conflict heterogeneity useful for vaccination programme planning and deployment. The granularity of the outputs produces more accurate mappings of unvaccinated children in conflict settings, supporting global vaccination and health equity goals.

KEYWORDS: vaccination, conflict, population, gridded estimates, global health

1. Introduction

Conflict, defined here as political violence, poses a significant threat to reaching global vaccination and health equity goals under the umbrella of SDG3 (Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance 2024; O'Brien et al. 2024; Ciccacci et al. 2025; Headley et al. 2025). Conflicts have both direct and indirect effects on vaccination programmes, and these effects differ across different conflict contexts (Okwo-Bele et al. 2018). However, a consistent, effective methodology for mapping children affected by conflict has not been developed, making it difficult to not only know how many unvaccinated children live in conflict settings but also understand the differences between these conflict settings so vaccination programmes can be effectively adapted to local contexts.

This paper proposes a new buffer-intensity method to generate gridded global conflict maps which are explicitly tailored for vaccination and healthcare studies. Resulting from a collaboration between WorldPop, Gavi the Vaccine Alliance (Gavi), the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) with further input from Armed Conflict Location & Event Data (ACLED), the results of this method incorporate both the geographic extent of conflict and conflict intensity into a gridded map (~1km²) of global conflict between 2022 and 2023. Intensity is calculated using multiple conflict attributes that impact vaccination rates. This method improves previous attempts to map conflict as it both captures the heterogeneity of conflicts while supporting multi-scalar analyses needed for effective vaccination programme planning.

2. Methodology

Population estimates for children under the age of 1 (PU1) came from mosaics that combined WorldPop Global2 constrained population estimates with bespoke age/sex disaggregated population estimates produced by WorldPop (Steingraber et al. 2025). Estimates for PU1 in 2023 were used in this analysis.

Conflict locations were obtained from ACLED website (ACLED 2024). ACLED data is recorded as

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points, with each point representing one conflict event on a single day. This project analyses all points with at least one fatality within the years 2022 and 2023.

Vaccination rates are adapted from estimates from IHME. IHME gridded ‘mean raked’ vaccination rates for the first and third doses of the diphtheria-tetanus-pertussis vaccines (DTP1, DTP3) and the measles containing vaccine (MCV1) in 75 countries (5km² scale) (Mosser 2024) were resampled to 1km and aligned with the latest WorldPop Global2 1km mastergrid. Rates of non-vaccination were obtained by finding the inverse of the original IHME rates. Estimates for 2023 were used in this analysis.

Adapting a method developed by WorldPop and ACLED (Raleigh et al. 2023), we modelled buffers with radii of 10km around each conflict point. The buffers were rasterized and then the coverage of each Global2 mastergrid cell was calculated as a proportion (0-1). This proportion was then multiplied by the PU1 population raster to count the number of children living within a conflict affected area.

A gridded conflict-intensity raster was also developed. Conflict intensity is often measured by fatalities (e.g. Headley et al 2025; Ostby et al 2020; Wagner et al 2019), but fatality numbers are notoriously unreliable (Raleigh 2023). Instead, our updated method for measuring conflict intensity is adapted from ACLED (ACLED 2025) and includes additional measures alongside deadliness. Our measure replaces ACLED’s diffusion with an event count measure deemed more appropriate for subnational analysis. Additionally, it replaces fragmentation with a measure of longevity, as prolonged conflicts are more likely to disrupt vaccination programmes (Okwo-Bele 2020).

This adapted measure of intensity was calculated by compiling a series of point statistics around each event using the 10km buffer. The statistics included:

- Event count: number of event buffers to overlay each grid cell
- Deadliness: sum of deaths associated with each buffer overlying each grid cell
- Danger: number of event buffers overlaying each grid cell associated with an event that targeted civilians
- Longevity: number of quarters (3-month periods) represented by the buffers overlying each grid cell that have had at least one conflict fatality over the course of the 2022-2023 period

The raster for each measure was normalised on a 0-1 scale using a min-max normalisation formula. The average of each of the values was calculated and then divided into classes.

3. Results

Preliminary results and validation illustrate the promise of this method. Sense-checks of this method in 75 countries across the globe illustrate that the dataset reflects well-known global patterns of conflict (Figure 1). Conflict was most intense in Palestine, Syria, El Salvador, Myanmar, Burundi, and Haiti. Moreover, the method also effectively captures the subnational heterogeneity of conflict (Figure 2). There are 724 adm2 districts where 100% of PU1 is in a conflict-affected area. 1,306 districts have 95% of their PU1 in a conflict-affected areas, and 1,584 districts have 80% of PU1 in conflict-affected areas. Of note, there are 24 adm2 districts with an average intensity score of 5 (the highest possible), which include 4 units from Haiti, 3 from Palestine, and 17 from Somalia.

Figure 1 The average intensity of conflict in populated areas for 2022 and 2023 in the 75 countries of the project.

We have validated the method using case studies in the Philippines, Afghanistan, Madagascar, and Somalia. Comparison with a fatality-based measure previously used by the team (Wigley et al. 2022) suggests the buffer-intensity method captures a larger number of children and a wider range of conflict settings, reflecting more closely the reality of conflict settings across the globe. The conflict-intensity score enables visualisation of the different characteristics of conflict and allow researchers to categorise children into useful subclasses (Table 1). It is also less prone the effects of population density which can cause some conflict-intensity methods to underestimate conflict intensity in densely populated areas.

Figure 2 Percentage of children under the age of one in 2023 living within 10km of a conflict occurring between 2022 and 2023 (by adm2).

Table 1 Population of unvaccinated children living in conflict-affected areas of each intensity value

Intensity Value	1	2	3	4	5	Total
All 75 Countries	2,464,056	1,044,240	684,135	916,862	186,205	5,295,498
Africa	1,704,030	781,107	481,839	526,425	145,295	3,638,696
Americas/ Caribbean	46,507	12,230	10,928	13,664	1,902	97,231
Asia/Oceania/E urope	713,519	250,903	191,368	376,773	27,008	1,559,571

4. Conclusion

Children in conflict-settings have proven to be one of the hardest groups of children to reach by vaccination programmes. A great barrier to reducing these numbers has been our ability to accurately predict both where and how many children have missed vaccinations due to conflict. This paper presents a new buffer-intensity methodology that improves our ability to accurately map children in conflict settings. It's granularity and integration of multiple conflict attributes preserves the heterogeneity of conflict typically seen in national or subnational research but allows research at global scales.

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7. Biographies

Dr Aubrey Steingraber has been working at WorldPop at the University of Southampton since 2023, first as a specialist GIS technician and currently as a research fellow. Before joining WorldPop, she had a background in archaeology and GIS and received her PhD from the University of York in 2022.

Natalia Tejedor-Garavito is a Principal Enterprise Fellow at WorldPop and leads the Geospatial Data and Analysis Team. Her work focuses on producing high resolution, open and contemporary data, mainly on projects related to reproductive, maternal, newborn, child, and adolescence health.